

Death and Exequies in the Sangam and Post-Sangam Tamil Tradition:
Social Norms, Beliefs and Practice

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ABSTRACT

Cultural history is a study of beliefs and ideas in a given time and space. It is important for a cultural historian to determine within that time and space whose voice they are listening to. Generalising values and ideas of a society without paying attention to the social and cultural nuances of each social group within it brings out erroneous values. Study of past societies in their context without passing judgement is imperative to the critical analysis of the cultural history of any specific society. Death and the rituals associated with death, the beliefs, and desires of a society on how they wished to die, bereavement and the social norms expected of the persons who had undergone a sense of loss and the stories of liminality of those who anticipate death brings out the cultural identity of a society.

Key Words: Death, Cultural History, Society

Introduction:

According to Peter Burke 'Cultural History is a method of research that presumes that there is incorrectness that binds together the personalities, events, monuments and so forth of a certain time and place. It possesses a primary degree of certainty, as it consists for the most part of material conveyed in an unintentional, disinterested or even involuntary way¹. The idea of culture implies the idea of tradition, of certain kinds of knowledge and skills handed down from one generation to the next. Since multiple traditions can easily coexist in the same society, the idea of tradition liberates cultural historians from the assumption of the unity or homogeneity of an 'age'. cultural history pays attention to varieties, debates, and conflicts but also to shared concerns and traditions. A cultural historian gets to parts of the past that other historians cannot reach. It probes the values held by particular groups in particular places and particular periods.².

The way humans have lineage, their thoughts, belief system and the practices based on those also have a lineage. People living in similar environments and bound by common values, belief systems bequeath legacies which are shared over centuries. Changes occur from time to time due to the change in the environment, in the belief system, and due to hierarchy within the society which favours some and suppresses some and keeps the society subservient to the interest of a few. But these changes over time become the norm and become part of the continuing tradition. Historical legacies are those invaluable links which connect the past to the present. They give a context to the beliefs and practices of a society which in turn makes the society who they are. It develops over time, social and cultural identity based on continuing traditions, change in traditions and even discontinued traditions.

Jason Wittenberg says that legacies are categorized into two: temporal which belongs to a particular period and functional being of a particular aspect. Any one period of the temporal dimension can have multiple legacies of the functional dimension. Similarly, one type of functional dimension may have multiple values of physical dimension. He says that it is important to distinguish between structural and cultural legacies, or between formal and

¹ Peter Burke, (second edition, 2008), "What is Cultural History", Cambridge, UK, Pp. 2-3.

² Ibid 25-26

informal legacies, or even between positive and negative legacies³ According to Charles R Conn legacy investigations are thoughtful community solutions seen in the context of promoting restorative justice, improving understanding, and building relationships between different identity groups⁴. He further states that one needs to explore the mechanisms while analysing historical legacies that is to examine the moral mechanisms and principles that seem to be at play at the time when the legacy was born⁵. According to Susan V Bosak, Legacy is an interconnection across time, with a need for those who have come before us and a responsibility to those who come after us. It is fundamental to what it is to be human. Without a sense of working to create a legacy, adults lose meaning in their life. Exploring the idea of legacy offers a glimpse not only into human relationships but builds strong communities and human spirit⁶.

How the Ancient Tamils looked at death and the rituals associated with it, the social norms adopted around the incident tell us what kind of a society it was, what the society believed in, over centuries what changed and what continued. This in turn helps us build the cultural identity the society believed in, built, and projected over centuries.

The objective of this research paper is to understand the cultural identity of the Tamils through the study of death and death rituals. Tamil literary works will be referred for this study, though excavation reports and epigraphs will be studied to supplement the inferences gleaned through the literature. The Sangam works (roughly 300 BCE to 300 CE) of Purananuru (Puram four hundred), Agananuru (Agam four hundred), Paripadal, Silapadikaram, Manimekalai and the post-Sangam literature (beyond 300 CE) comprising of Jeevaka Chintamani, Valayapati, Kundalakesi, Ula literature, and Periya Puranam form the base of this research article.

³ Jason Wittenberg, “What is a Historical Legacy”, University of California, Berkley, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228256216_What_is_a_Historical_Legacy. Accessed on 11th May 2023

⁴ Charles R Conn, (2018), “Thinking About Historical Legacies: Looking for Just Principles and Process”, Occasional Paper I, Institute of Historical Justice and Reconciliation, <https://www.rhodeshouse.ox.ac.uk/media/45551/charles-conn-thinking-about-historical-legacies.pdf>

⁵ Ibid

⁶ Susan Bosak,” What is Legacy”, <https://www.legacyproject.org/guides/whatislegacy.html>, accessed on 24th August 2023

Authors who have written on the history of ancient Tamilnadu have written on topics such as sati and hero stones which are very valuable. Krishnaswami Aiyangar in his Ancient India says that self-immolation cannot be equated with sati. As he says that both men and women have taken their life for various reasons, and all have to be considered as self-immolation and sati was just one aspect of it. This view has not been seconded by anyone else. Nilakanta Sastri has talked about the practice of Sati in some detail in his book '*The Colas*'. He rightly asserts that it was not a common practice though it was prevalent through the centuries. In his other work "*The Pandyan Kingdom*", he has written a chapter on Marco Polo's observations on the Pandyan kingdom. Marco Polo talks about the King's Barons. He says that 'they always rode with him, always were near him and had great authority in the kingdom. They were called the king's Trusty Lieges. When the king died, they put him on fire to burn him. These Lieges cast themselves into the fire round about his body and suffer themselves to be burnt along with him. For they say they have been comrades in this world, and that they also ought to keep in company in the other world'⁷. Sastri says the mention of Tennavan Appattudavigal in the epigraphs attest to the observation made by Marco Polo. Marco Polo also mentions 'the practice of sati and the practice of allowing the condemned criminal to sacrifice himself to some God or the other of his choice'⁸. In his work "*The Colas*", Sastri says the term Velaikkarar are comparable with the Tennavan Appattudavigal and they were the most permanent and dependable troops in the royal service, and their designation implies that they were ever ready to defend the king and his cause with their lives when occasion arose⁹. In her work "*Administration and Social Life under the Pallavas*" C. Minakshi makes a fleeting mention of the practice of sati and talks at length about the practices relating to remembrance of the dead in the Pallava times. According to her 'the preservation of the memory of the dead through visible acts such as charitable endowments, raising of portrait statues, and erection of monuments and temples on the tombs of the dead was an ancient custom'. She sites the examples of 'Matangan Palli' and the feudatory chieftain Rajaditya building a memorial and a Shiva temple in memory of his father Prithvi Gangarayar¹⁰ and the

⁷ K.A. Nilakanta Sastri, (1929), "*The Pandyan Kingdom from the Earliest Times to the Sixteenth Century*", London, Pp. 196-197

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ K.A. Nilakanta Sastri (1955), "*The Colas*", University of Madras, Madras, P.454

¹⁰ C. Minakshi, (1938), "*Administration and Social Life under the Pallavas*", University of Madras, Madras, Pp. 163-165

appearance of many hero stones during the later Pallava period¹¹. There are a number of books written in Tamil which are helpful in understanding the social life of the Tamils. “*Ayirathennuru Andugallukku Murpatta Tamilagam*” by Appaturai talks about the unique practice among the men in the Sangam period, quoted from Kalithogai, wherein the man pining with unrequited love would make a horse made of palm stems, he would decorate it with beads and peacock feather and take it around the town while singing songs in praise of his love and his lover. If the girl responded to it, it would end in marriage otherwise the man would fall from a height and commit suicide¹². “*Sangakala Vazhviyal*” by N. Subramanian talks about the wife dying out of remorse when the husband had died in a battlefield or she committing sati. He also explains the rigours of widowhood¹³. “*Tirunavalur*” by S. Paranan, the book being a publication by Tamilnadu Archaeological Department, talks about urn burials in Tirunavalur which is located in Kallakurichi district. According to the author many urns have been found in the fields and in residential areas in this town and also in the neighbouring villages. In 1875 J.H. Garstin, an archaeologist found a mud sarcophagus¹⁴. “*Bhakti Ilakkiyatil Samudaya Parvai*” by T. Isawarapillai has brought out social aspects in Bhakti literature especially from Periya Puranam.

Manimekalai gives the description of Chakravalakottam in Puhar. According to it, there were four doorways in Chakravalakottam. One of them had the stucco figurine of a Goblin which had folded red lips, a terrifying stare, noose on one hand and a trident on the other. Leading from the doorway was a spacious temple for Durga. Around that there were many brick memorials for kings, hermits, and women who died with their husbands for whom their families had built these structures according to each social grouping’s tradition. There were pillars where sacrifice (animal) was done for gods. The place abounds in many stone benches, winding pathways, residential huts for the keepers of the place, their wooden staves, and the vessels they used to eat food being strewn around everywhere, the glowing embers from the burning bodies being carried by the wind. Many kinds of death rituals were practiced. The bodies were burnt, or they were left there for the animals and birds to eat, or they were buried, or they were left sealed in naturally inclined spots, or they were buried in urns. People

¹¹ Ibid, Pp. 165-168

¹² K. Appadurai, (2003), “*Ayirathonnuru Andugallukku Murpatta Tamilagam*”, Chennai, Pp.195-196

¹³ N. Subramanian, (reprint 2019), “*Sangakala Vazhviyal*”, Chennai, Pp. 391- 396

¹⁴ S. Paranan, (2006) (Tamil), “*Tirunavalur*”, Tamilnadu Department of Archaeology, Chennai, Pp. 134-135

were moving in and out through the day and night. The place was filled with wailing sounds of the kin of the dead, and the prayer sounds of the followers at memorials for the hermits, howling sound of the foxes, hooting of the owls, the hoot of the Kottān (a kind of an owl) which eats human flesh, and the chirp of the blue flycatcher which pecks the skull to eat the brain. The place abounded with Vagai (walnut) trees, frangipani, and Vila (wood apple) trees. Some lived there to fulfil vows, they arranged the burnt skulls to make a garland, and a few cooked the flesh in the Vellidai Mantap. Byers, and the pots filled with embers of fire, tied cloth, rice, and puffed rice, small mud pots were strewn here and there¹⁵. This scenario is briefly described in Puram poems too¹⁶.

Philosophy of Birth, Death, and Rebirth:

King Koperuncholan had a serious disagreement with his sons regarding succession. His first thought was to quell the rebellious forces of his sons with his royal forces. But his friend and poet Pisirandhaiyar wisely counselled him against it. According to him, only his enemies would be happy about a situation wherein the father killed both the heirs to the throne. In case, if he lost, it would mar his prestige. Hence, to overcome this challenge successfully, he advised the king to do the penance of ‘vadakiruthal’ which is losing life by sitting facing north and stop eating. He convinced the Chola king that this way he would be able to maintain his glory after life. Accepting that Kopperuncholan started the penance. Before starting the penance, the king expounded the philosophy of life and death to those who discouraged him from starting it.

‘Those who tried to hunt an elephant may get successful as compared to a person who tried to hunt a small bird (Those who aim high may be more successful than those who aim small). Those who undertake the penance will attain everlasting joy and eternity. Those who attained eternity will not be born again and they will attain everlasting glory’¹⁷.

¹⁵ U.V. Swaminathaiyar, (2013), (Tamil), “Manimekalai” Chakkaravalakottamuraita kadai, Chennai, Verse lines 1-115, Pp. 66-76.

¹⁶ Manickam A., (ed.), (Tamil), (1990), “Purananuru: Poems and commentary”, Part II, Chennai, Verses 359, Pp. 263-265

¹⁷ Ibid, “Purananuru: Poems and commentary”, Verses 213-222, Pp. 31- 46

Not being able to leave his friend alone Pisirandhaiyar also joined him. Both died as a result of this penance and attained everlasting glory as they desired. Their friendship is extolled even to the present day.

One of the Puram poem philosophises thus: those kings who considered all lands as their own died, their treasures were of no use to them in their last moments, with their kin wailing when they breathed their last nothing except their good deeds were their companion. Those who rejected it while they were living lost their chance to attain eternity¹⁸.

A poet cautions the king saying ‘very few kings did charity to the poor, were sensitive to the needs of those who were starving, could converse with kindness, did meritorious things that benefitted the larger society and worked for stability in where they ruled. Many do not know how to acquire these qualities. Their position and wealth won’t be stable. So, one should do their duty, and do charity. Even after seeing the dead being taken to the crematorium in a byer which is full of shrubs, where the living serve toddy and cooked rice (where the body kept on a bed of dharba or Tussock grass) after eating which it (the body) is consigned to flames, people have not turned to the path righteousness’¹⁹.

Iyati Venteriyar, a poet addresses a king as thus: ‘Many kings have ruled this world without sharing with others. Even they did not last forever. When they died, their remains were taken to the burning grounds full of wild shrubs, where the keeper of the crematorium served saltless cooked food on the ground to the dead without turning back. Everyone one day has to accept this offering served reluctantly by the keeper. So, before that day comes leave your attachments’²⁰.

Valayapati, the post-sangam Jaina literature says that to stop the cycle of birth and death one should stop having attachment to material things. For such a person, even his body is a burden. When one loses interest in his person, he would lose interest in material possessions and that is the way to attain eternity²¹

¹⁸ Ibid, Verse 357, Pp. 259-261.

¹⁹ Ibid, Verse 360, Pp. 266-267

²⁰ Ibid, Verse 363, PP. 272-273

²¹ V.T. Subramaniyam, (2000), (Tamil), “Valayapati, Kundalakesi: Poem and Commentary”, Valayapati, Chennai, Verse 42, P. 42

The author of Kundalakesi wonders that from the time when a foetus gets formed in the mother's womb it undergoes change and keeps progressing to the next stage. A foetus is born as an infant, the infant becomes the child, the child becomes the youth, The strength and attraction of this phase progresses to the young man becoming old and infirm. No one complains about these progressions but when the end comes people blame the lord of death and feel remorse!²²

King Sachchandan expounds the philosophy of birth, death, and rebirth to his queen Vijayai just before being killed by his commander in Jeevaka Chintamani. Accordingly:

*'Birth, acquiring wealth, losing it, being in love, falling out of love and death happens because of one's past deeds. We cannot count the number of times we were born before. We were not together in those lives. In the forthcoming lives we may again not meet each other. We lived together for a short span of time. Do not aspire for permanency in this transient relationship'*²³.

In the same work Sachchandan's son king Jeevakan decided to renounce worldly life and preferred attaining keval gnayan. He met two ascetics who explained to him about his previous life. Accordingly, in his previous life Jeevakan was a prince. His queens wanted to keep some cygnets as pets and hence, he separated them from their mother. The story implies that this act of separating the cygnets from the mother swan led to Jeevakan being separated from his mother at birth²⁴.

Hero Stones:

If a king or a warrior died in a battle, people installed a hero stone in his memory, dressed it with peacock feathers, washed it every morning and gave offerings of rice and meat²⁵. Some worshipped it as God in preference to the worship of any other gods²⁶.

²² Ibid, Kundalakesi, Verse 7, P.7

²³ Durai Rajaram, (ed.), (Tamil), (Reprint 2016), "Jeevaka Chintamani", Mullai Publications, Chennai, Volume 1, Verse 268-272.

²⁴ Op. Cit., "Jeevaka Chintamani", Volume 6, Verse 2857-2880, Pp. 200-209.

²⁵ Ibid, Verse 329, Pp. 216-217

²⁶ Ibid, Verse 335, Pp. 224-225

Vadamodhankizhar, a poet in Thondainadu²⁷ started to meet his patron who was also a warrior. When he started from his house, he could not properly strum his string instrument (Yazh), and he also crossed a woman who had left her hair unbraided (these two were considered as bad omen). When he reached the patron's village, he heard the news that latter had died in a battle that ensued after a cattle raid in which after killing a few, the warrior had died and in the place where he died people had installed a hero stone in which his exploits were inscribed, and the stone being adorned with a peacock feather being under a cloth canopy²⁸. Another poem describes a similar situation wherein a warrior died while preventing a cattle raid. The villagers installed a hero stone and when they met a bard told him to pay his reverence to the hero stone and sing his praise so that the region would get rain and there would be greenery resulting in prosperity²⁹. Since, Kopperuncholan spent his last days in a small place a stele or *nadugal* was installed there to spread his fame³⁰. Similarly, when Adigaman of Thagadur died his mortal remains were consigned to flames and a stele was installed to commemorate his life³¹.

Honour in Death:

Honour based cultures believe in dying if they are not able to fulfil acts which they consider virtuous. Welcoming death redeems men from the fear of failure. Almost everything including lack of strategy in war, inflexibility in approach, and non-acceptance of inevitability get glossed over once the person chooses death over living.

In the Sangam period, when a soldier joins the war, the king would welcome him by offering him toddy. This was considered an honour. If the soldier had any special credentials such as someone in the soldier's family had already died in a previous battle, then the king would honour him by pouring him special toddy which was highly intoxicating³².

²⁷ Thondainadu comprised areas from Northern Tamilnadu comprising of Kanchipuram and nearby areas including parts of southern Seema Andhara. Modern capital Chennai was part of this region

²⁸ Op. Cit., "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Part II, Verse 260, Pp. 113-116.

²⁹ Ibid, Verse 263, Pp. 120-122

³⁰ Ibid, "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Part II, Verse 212-216, Pp. 29-39.

³¹ Ibid Verse 232, Pp. 64-65

³² Op. Cit., "Purananuru: Poems and commentary" Verse 290, Pp. 161-162.

Dying in warfare was considered the best way to die for men and especially so for the kings. Such kings invariably attained heaven. Jeevaka Chintamani describes the scene of king Sachchandana's death as the warrior taking the blow of the enemy, being pierced by sharp lancers, fell to the ground with his back pressing the bosom of the earth goddess while keeping his angry eyes wide open³³.

Exequies:

Purananuru, the Sangam book of four hundred poems on various aspects of contemporary life repeatedly talks about Exequies practiced by the contemporary society. People were either buried in an urn or they were consigned to flames. Though the mortal remains of the kings were burnt some were buried in urns.

Kings were expected to die in a battle as death due to old age or natural causes was considered an unhonourable way of passing away. To wipe away the humiliation of natural death the body was either cut to pieces or skull was broken with a sword before burial. King Nambi Nedunchezhiyan, a chieftain, passed away due to natural causes. As he was a great warrior the poet Perayil Muruvalar suggested that his skull be broken with a sword or with a lancer before either consigning the mortal remains to the flames or it be buried in an urn³⁴.

When a man died, his wife or wives wailed beating their chests and breaking their bangles. This was considered as the appropriate behaviour by the Sangam poets. The next day the women were expected to clean a spot the size of an elephant's foot and keep offerings of cooked rice for the departed soul. When king Velliman died and was buried in an urn, his queens broke their bangles and beat their chests in despair³⁵. It also talks about the queens of Karikala Chola who ruled Uraiyur in the 2nd Century CE taking off their jewellery and breaking their bangles when he died³⁶.

³³ Op. Cit., "Jeevaka Chintamani", Volume 1, Verse 288-289.

³⁴ Op. Cit., "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Verse 239, Pp. 75-78

³⁵ Ibid "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Verse 237-238, Pp. 71-75

³⁶ Ibid Verse 224, PP. 48-49

Both poets Kiran and Mudamosiyar note in separate verses the death of the king Ay Andiran and his queens committing sati by plunging into the pyre³⁷.

Manimekalai narrates the story of Adirai who believed that her husband had passed away during sea travel. She decided to commit sati despite others discouraging her. But at the time she tries to enter the pyre she sees good omen. So, she accepted others' advice and stepped back. Later she realises that her husband was alive.

On one occasion, when the queen died the king too thought of self-immolation but was restrained by others who reminded him of his kingly duties. When Seraman Makkodhai's queen died and the remains were consigned to flames, the king considered self-immolation but was prevented by others around citing his duty towards his country³⁸³⁹.

When the Sangam Chola king Killivalavan died, the poet out of remorse address the poem to the potter describing the stature and prowess of the late king and asks whether he could make such a big pot that would accommodate the mortal remains of the king⁴⁰.

When Sachchandan died in the warfare, his mortal remains were consigned to flames by pouring pots of ghee and other flammable ingredients. His queens broke their bangles, necklaces and threw away their ear studs and head jewellery, removed the flowers they had worn on their hair and wailed loudly⁴¹.

One of his queens Vijayai, was pregnant and hearing the news she delivered a baby which she gave to a merchant in adoption and entered a Jain ashram as a mendicant to observe penance⁴².

Omen of death:

³⁷ Ibid "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Verse 240-241, Pp. 78-81

³⁸ Op. Cit. Manimegalai, Adhirai Pichaiyitta Kadhai, Pp. 169-177

³⁹ Ibid "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Verse 245, 86-88

⁴⁰ Ibid Verse 228, Pp. 56-57

⁴¹ Ibid Verses 265 & 266

⁴² Op. Cit., "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Part II, Verse 223. Pp. 46-47

Sangam Tamils believed in omens both good and bad. Before every activity they checked the movement of birds, stars, and other natural occurrences. It is based on these predictions they started work⁴³.

Poet Arisil Kizhar says that just before the death of Ezhini, the ruler of Thagadur, a flaming star fell on the sea in the month of Panguni (February-March). The Sangam people believed that if a star fell on earth in the month Panguni it would fatally affect the ruler. At the same time, the elephants spread themselves on the ground with their trunk into the earth, the drum leather was torn, the royal parasol was broken, the royal horses had no strength to gallop.

When the man of the house had gone to wage a war, the lady of the house bunched the leaves of the neem tree with the Irava tree and hung it at the house entrance, fried white mustard in ghee and sprinkled it all over the house, smoked Akhil incense to spread fragrance, made a lute out of water lily leaves and blew it, chimed the bell, and to the tune of Yazh and sang the Kanchi pann with the belief these will ward off unfortunate events at home and his wounds would not turn fatal⁴⁴. Another poem says all the men of the village had gone to participate in a war and hence, in every house these rituals were practised⁴⁵.

Widowhood:

Social norms are the accepted behaviour at any given situation and at any place by a person or a group. Appropriateness in public behaviour rewards social acceptability and sometimes honour and prestige within the community and the larger society. The person who confirms social norms also sets a benchmark for others to follow.

‘Social norms are the perceived informal, mostly unwritten, rules that define acceptable and appropriate actions within a given group or community, thus guiding human behaviour. They consist of what we do, what we believe others do, and what we believe others approve of and expect us to do. Social norms are therefore situated at the interplay between behaviour, beliefs, and expectations. A social norm exists when individuals practise a behaviour because they believe that others like them or in their community practise the behaviour (descriptive

⁴³ Ibid, “Purananuru: Poems and commentary”, Part II, Verse 229, PP. 57-61

⁴⁴ Ibid, Verse 281, Pp. 147-148.

⁴⁵ Ibid, Verse 296, Pp. 169-170

*norms), or because they believe that those who matter to them approve of them practising the behaviour*⁴⁶.

Like men, women of the Sangam period sought honour in death. When the husband died women had two choices: self-immolation (*Sati*) or practicing rigorous tents of widowhood. Some Puram poems indicate that when the husband died the wife had volunteered to be buried with him in the urn⁴⁷. Silapadigaram states that when the Pandyan king died in despair realising that he had taken an innocent life due to error in judgement, his queen also followed suit⁴⁸. Many scholars believe that she must have committed sati. Puram literature gives many examples where the queens of dead kings committed Sati. This practice, though not widespread, was prevalent even during the early medieval period and it was a popular reaction amongst the queens and the women of the trading community. But majority of them led a life of severe austerities suffering self and community induced sufferings including self-loathing.

When Budha Pandiyan died his mortal remains were consigned to flames in front of Devi temple. His wife Perungopendu decided to commit sati. She took bath and with dripping hair went inside the temple to pray. Many wisemen dissuaded her from doing so as she understood politics very well and was capable of leading the country to betterment. She admonished them saying instead of encouraging her to commit sati the wisemen were misleading her. Did they expect her to lead the rest of her life in austerity by not eating ghee and having cooked rice soaked in water with cooked pasalai leaves (Indian spinach, Basella Alba) mixed with tamarind and gingelly paste? Did they also expect her to sleep on stone bed without any bedding and live like other widowed women⁴⁹? Periyapuram narrates the story of Tirunavukkarasar whose period is estimated to be around 7th century CE. It says when Tirunavukkarasar was a child when his sister Tilakavati who was twelve years of age was betrothed to be married to Kalipagai, a warrior. But before the marriage could be solemnised their father dies; their mother commits sati. Kalipagai participated in a war and died. Tilakavati decided that being betrothed was as good as being married and decided to commit

⁴⁶ UNICEF – definition of social norms <https://www.unicef.org/media/111061/file/Social-norms-definitions-2021.pdf>, accessed on 24th August 2023

⁴⁷ Op. Cit., “Purananuru: Poems and commentary”, Part II, Verse 256, 105-107

⁴⁸ Op. Cit., Silapadigaram Pp. 310-314

⁴⁹ Op. Cit., “Purananuru: Poems and commentary”, Part II, Verse 246-47, PP. 88-91

sati. But Tirunavukkarasar pleaded with her not to leave him alone. So, she practiced widowhood⁵⁰. Many Chola queens committed sati when their husbands passed away though there was the example of Sembiyan Madevi who spent her time in temple renovation and charities. When Sundaracholan (Paranthaka II 958-973 CE), died his queen Vananvan Madhevi committed sati⁵¹. Rajendra Chola's queen too committed sati⁵². Similarly, when Rajaraja II died in 1173 CE his four queens committed sati⁵³. Nilakanta Sastri opines that though sati was prevalent it was not common practice⁵⁴.

Masathanar, a poet, speaks of a young woman addressing the white-water Lily (Ambal) saying the seeds within the flower served as rice (pullarisi) for her⁵⁵. Widowed women were not allowed to eat paddy rice, so they had to use such seeds as grains for their food. Similarly, another woman who always served paddy rice and milk for every guest, after the demise of her husband appeared with tonsured head, eating inferior quality rice with hand which was devoid of bangles⁵⁶. A similar sentiment is expressed in another poem wherein the lady after her husband's death tells the bard that she wouldn't like to live the life of austerity where she had to forgo wearing ornaments, tonsure her head and eat inferior quality rice and instead would prefer dying⁵⁷. Another woman who finds her dead husband in a battlefield laments as to how she would show her hands which were devoid of bangles to his relatives⁵⁸.

When Vijayai, the queen of Sachchandan in Jeevaka Chintamani was widowed she gives her son in adoption to a merchant for the fear of the child being killed by enemies, she then took the guidance of a sagely woman, who told her not to stay in the kingdom after the death of the husband. So, she moved to the forest and reached a Jain hermitage where she broke her bangles and one by one cast aside her jewellery with the help of the women mendicants on a

⁵⁰ A. Manikkanar (ed.), (1990), (Tamil), "Periyapuranam: Text and Commentary", Volume II, Verses 1282-1299, Chennai, PP. 235-243

⁵¹ SII Volume VII, NO. 863, T. Eshwaranpilai, (2000), "Bhakti Ilakkiyatil Samudhaya Parvai", Thanjavur, Pp. 232-233

⁵² Ibid, Bhakti Ilakkiyatil Samudhaya Parvai",

⁵³ N. Sethuraman, (1989), (Tamil), Sankara Cholan Ula, Kulothunga Cholan Kovai", Pp. 21-23

⁵⁴ "The Colas", Pp. 553-554.

⁵⁵ Ibid, "Purananuru: Poems and commentary", Part II, Verse 248, P95-96

⁵⁶ Ibid, Verse 250, Pp. 96-97

⁵⁷ Ibid, Verse 280, Pp. 144-147

⁵⁸ Ibid Verse 253, Pp. 100-101

day when the moon was waxing and became a mendicant. It is after seeing her child grow up and becoming a king, she became an ascetic.

Liminality and spiritual realm:

Tamil literature brings out many incidents wherein an individual gets into a transitory phase before passing over to a spiritual realm. Bhakti literature is full of such narration. Even secular works such as Silapadhikaram and Jeevaka Chintamani narrate a stunning psychological transformation an individual undergoes before they pass over to the other realm. Three such incidences have been taken up for discussion.

Silapdikaram, dated between 3rd to 5th century CE tells the story of Kannagi, the heroine from the trading community. Her husband Kovalan finds love in the companionship of Madhavi, danseuse par excellence. Kannagi waits for many years alone and longing for her indifferent husband to take interest in her. He finally returns home, broken both financially and in spirit. Both travel to Madurai to start a new life. She gives Kovalan one of her expensive anklets to start some trading activity. When he goes to sell it in the market he gets killed in a case of mistaken identity. The news of her husband's death completely transforms the nature of Kannagi from one of timidity and obedience to a woman full of anger seeking vengeance. She proves to the Pandyan king that he made a mistake by killing her husband. He dies immediately out of remorse. His queen shortly dies not wanting to live after him. Kannagi then plucks one of her breasts and throws it out cursing the city would be destroyed. The palace catches fire, and it spreads to the city. Many die while many others escape. It is after this she leaves the city of Madurai. As the author recounts her tale:

'She came from the eastern gate but left the city of Madurai from the western gate. She went to the temple of Korravai and broke her bangles and set out to meet her dead husband on the advice of Madurapati, a divine woman. She kept walking along the banks of river Vaigai and started ascending the hills. She kept ascending and descending as the path of the river would take her for many days. She then reached a spot in the hills where she sat under a Vengai tree (Pterocarpus marsupium). When the local tribe saw her, she appeared calm but looked distressed. When they enquired about her whereabouts, she said that she lost her husband due to the misjudgement of the Pandyan king and all these happened due to her past life deeds and due to bad times of the Pandyan king. She identified herself as Pandyan's

daughter. She said that she was waiting for the full moon day when with her husband she would ascend to heaven. Surely, she did so, on the full moon day of the month of Ashad’.

After leaving the city of Madurai, Kannagi walks a distance of roughly 154 kilometres following the river Vaigai. In the upper reaches of the river, she follows one of the tributaries and reaches the place which is now in Idukki district of Kerala. According to the author, ‘for days she ascended and descended the hills and by the time the villagers met her she had calmed down but looked terrifying and was remote’. The fact that she travelled alone in a densely forested hilly region which was full of wild animals especially ferocious tigers did not matter to her. She was looking forward to the end of her worldly life awaiting her dead husband to take her to heaven.

The main protagonist of Jeevaka Chintamani, Jeevakan was the son of Sachchandan, who at birth had lost his kingdom to his father’s general. As a grownup man he fought a battle, killed the general and became the king. He then married eight women with whom he led a pleasurable life. Each one bore him a child. His life then on was one of war, peace, prosperity, and pleasure. It is after meeting his biological mother Vijayai, he understood the non-permanency of material pleasures. He then bade farewell to his wives after advising them on the futility of chasing pleasures and the merits of doing charity. The dispirited women also became hermits.

‘Jeevakan got into the palanquin to go to the temple of Arugar (Arihant). At that time everywhere the fragrance of Akil spread and the sound of stringed instruments and drums could be heard, the way to his journey looked festive, bees were humming, and flags were fluttering. It was then Lord Varadhaman appeared like the sun on top of the ruby mountain. The radiance of his face made Jeevakan realise that those who are rid of two kinds of deeds would glow like this. In His presence, Jeevakan was rid of his past deeds. He sang in praise of the lord and circumambulated the temple. Celestials gathered around the lord and were fanning him. The Ashoka tree under which the lord was seated looked festive. Jeevakan went near the lord. The celestials then whispered his clan and the gotra. Jeevakan expressed a wish to become a hermit and the lord smiled and said so be it. Jeevakan praised the grace of the lord, and he discarded his robes and shone like the sun. He plucked his hair one by one. He then joined the order of monks and started doing penance. He became enlightened and

attained Keval gnyan. His disciples praised his discourses as Anekanandvad. He then attained Parinirvana’.

The story of Gnanasampandhar, the gifted poet saint, who is considered one among the Triumvirate of the Saiva Bhakti Movement who lived in about 7th century CE, is mentioned in Periya Puranam, the 12th century work by Sekkizhar. In this, the author explains in detail the marriage preparations of Sambandhar in detail.

‘Sivapada Hridhayar and others took the consent of Ganansampandhar for his marriage. The elders found the daughter of Nambandar Nambi of Tirunallur Perumanam as the suitable alliance for Sampandhar. They decided to perform the marriage shortly as per the date and time fixed by those well versed in reading ephemeris. They then decorated the village of Thirunallur Perumanam for the marriage and for receiving many guests. The sacred thread was taken ceremoniously by the Brahmins well versed in Vedas and they tied it on Sampandhar’s wrist. The next day, the city woke up to the auspicious beats of drums in Tirunallur Perumanam. Many from various cities had to come to attend the wedding. Sampandhar visited the temple of Lord Shiva first and thereafter he went to a mutt where the Brahmins, well versed in decorating the groom dressed him for the occasion. He was then ceremoniously taken to the wedding hall which was filled with the fragrance of aromatic powders. The marriage took place amidst the recitation of Veda mantras by performing havan. When Sampandhar took the seven steps with the bride he decided that he would attain the Holy feet of the lord with his bride. He then along with his relatives and the guests visited the temple of Perumanam. There he sang the Padhigam Kallur Perumanam. He prayed for attaining the feet of the lord at that very moment. The voice of the lord commanded him, his wife and all those who attended the wedding to get into the shining light that suddenly appeared in the shape of a shivling. Its dazzling effulgence mesmerised everyone in the temple. Sampandhar asked everyone to get into the doorway within the light. After everyone entered and dissolved into the light, holding the hand of his bride he circumambulated the glowing light before entering it. He then became one with the lord and with that the light ceased to exist⁵⁹.

⁵⁹ Op. Cit., “Periya Puranam : Text and Commentary”, Volume V, Verses 3040 – 3154, PP. 51-101

In all the three stories the protagonists are considered real people who lived in the early years of the common era. Unlike Sampanthar the other two led worldly life but a thought or a crisis completely changed their life. They transformed in the liminal phase to enter into the spiritual realm. In the case of Sampanthar, he was considered a prodigy and later a genius. People around him believed he was gifted and was divine. At the end not only, he passed over to the spiritual realm but facilitated the passover of the entire retinue which followed him. This belief of humans becoming divine towards the end of their life journey is reflected in many literature particularly so in the post-Sangam literature.

To conclude, Though the Tamil society was quite orthodox in the treatment of women and widows, they had many rights which have also been described in the Sangam and post-Sangam works but that does not come under the scope of this study. Similarly, though undocumented, the practice of widows remarrying must have prevailed within some social groups. Since it went against the prevailing social norms it must not have been documented.

Many beliefs regarding death and after life are still believed by people. Exequies described in the Sangam and post-Sangam works are still being followed. Some practices such as secondary burials, urn burials have been discontinued. Due to the concerted efforts of social reformers in the 19th and the 20th centuries legislations against the practice of Sati were enacted. Coupled with social awareness the Tamil society has distanced itself from such practices. Even in the treatment of widows a major change has happened over time. Being a widow is not such a terrifying experience to many. Women accept widowhood with equanimity. Contemporary society is more kind to them than ever before. Young women remarry and that has wide acceptance in the society. Comparing the historical legacy of Tamil death and death rituals with other cultures to find similarities and differences is another area of research that needs to be undertaken in detail.